

MODELING OF HEAT TRANSFER AND UNSATURATED FLOW IN WOVEN FIBER REINFORCEMENTS DURING DIRECT INJECTION-PULTRUSION PROCESS OF THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this work, a modeling of the thermoplastic pultrusion process is presented. Pultrusion is a continuous manufacturing process of composites profiles with constant cross-sections. The process development with thermoplastics raises new issues concerning the impregnation step.

The study is focused on the heated die where several physics are involved. A heat transfer model is implemented and validated thanks to temperature measurements done on a pultrusion line. Then a dual scale flow approach is chosen to model the polymer flow within the woven fibers. A coupling between heat transfer and flow models is done through a viscosity temperature dependent. Data were measured on a pultrusion line and micrographs confirmed the modeling strategy. Through image analysis saturation degrees were measured to validate the models. The results show the importance of the die geometry choice and the control of the temperature distribution within the die.

Such models help to better understand the thermoplastic pultrusion process, to optimize the process parameters. The final goal is to manufacture pultruded profiles with the lowest residual porosity with pulling speeds compatible with an industrial process (speeds > 1 m/min).

1 INTRODUCTION

Injection-pultrusion is a manufacturing process in which continuous fibers impregnated with a liquid polymer are pulled through a die to form composites with a constant cross-section. Even though the impregnation step was not challenging with thermosets because of their low viscosity, it becomes a critical issue with melted thermoplastics due to their higher viscosity. A good understanding of the impregnation step is needed to limit the void formation.

Thermoplastic pultrusion with prepreg products such as commingled yarns or powder-impregnated bundles have already been studied, however there are very few reported works on direct impregnation with injection within the die. In addition, the rare studies have not adequately addressed the issue of unsaturated flow in woven fibers [1]. Only one scale was considered for the flow modeling. But a woven fabric is a porous medium with two scales of porosity: inter-tow volumes and intra-tow volumes.

The purpose of this study is to show the importance of the dual scales and the temperature on the polymer flow and especially the impact on the residual porosity in the pultruded profile.

The solution proposed here, models the polymer flow through a dual-scale porous medium [2]. A heat transfer model is coupled to a mesoscopic flow model enriched with a sink term. Specific changes of variables are made so as to model the steady state solution of unsaturation along a continuous process.

The flow modeling coupled to heat transfer of the thermoplastic pultrusion process aims at determining the saturation evolution through the die. The influence of several process parameters are

analyzed in this paper. Data are measured on a pultrusion line and micrographs are used to validate the models.

2 EXPERIMENTAL WORK

2.1 Material

The experimental tests were performed with multi-axial (0° , 90°) plain weave glass fiber tapes (woven ribbons) with an areal weight of 800 g/m^2 and 50 or 100 mm in width. These woven ribbons will be called tapes in the following. The matrix was a high fluidity PA66 supplied by Solvay. It has a viscosity around $15 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$ at 280°C . Compared to usual PA66 whose viscosity ranges from 200 to $300 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$, the high fluidity allows direct injection pultrusion to be carried out.

2.2 Processing technology

A schematic view of the pultrusion line used during the study is shown in Figure 1. Dry tapes are pulled from several creels with a pulling mechanism. They are gathered before entering into a preheating system. The preheating is necessary to enhance the impregnation and to avoid too high temperature differences between fiber reinforcements and polymer. Then the tapes enter the heated die where the molten polymer is injected. The impregnation step takes place in the tapered portion of the heated die. There, the fiber/polymer system is compressed until the final profile geometry is reached (consolidation). The conformation happens at the exit of the die in the straight portion. It is where the exact geometry of the profile cross-section is formed. The cooling die at the end is necessary for thermoplastic pultrusion. In this region, the fiber/polymer system is solidified and the profile that emerges from the die is crystallized.

The pultrusion line was used to produce samples with rectangular cross-section (flat profiles with thickness of 3.2 mm and 5 plies) and omega cross-section (with a thickness of 4 mm and 7 plies). The targeted fiber volume fraction was between 45 and 55%.

Figure 1 : Schematic for direct injection pultrusion for thermoplastics

3 HEAT TRANSFER

The heat transfer modeling is the first step of the study. The flow model will be coupled to the heat transfer model within the heated die so it is necessary to have an accurate prediction of the temperature distribution within the tapes. The early work by Aström and Pipes [4] is used to implement the model along the heated die. Temperature measurements were done on the pultrusion line to validate the model.

3.1 2D model

Aström and Pipes [4] proposed a model with a one-dimensional transient heat transfer equation. They considered the pultrusion process of thermoplastic matrix composites reinforced by unidirectional fibers. In their case, prepreg tows enter into the die so they supposed an intimate contact between matrix and fibers was initially assured. In [4], 2D geometry was considered for the die as shown in Figure 2. The height of the die was supposed small compared to the width so the heat

transfer in the y direction could be neglected. Moreover the height of the die was also small compared to its length so they considered the fibers nearly parallel to the x axis and the composite was treated as a transversely isotropic material. The major assumptions of the heat transfer analysis were that x -axis conduction and polymer flow were negligible and that the fiber/polymer system could be considered as a homogeneous material. Moreover it was also assumed that the temperature was independent of the pressure and the viscous dissipation was negligible. Focusing on the heated die Aström and Pipes [4] simplified the model a bit further and also neglected sources arising from the melting and crystallization.

Figure 2: Boundary conditions applied to the heated die domain for the heat transfer model

The startup of the process is a transient state when the heaters have just been turned on. But after a time long enough the composite travels through the die at a constant speed U and the process parameters remain constant (such as the temperature of the die walls) and the process is at steady state. Aström and Pipes studied the process without considering the transient state, they assumed the process at steady state.

The relation between the time and the x coordinate is given by $x = Ut$. Therefore the heat transfer equation may be written with spatial dependency $T(x, z)$:

$$\rho c U \frac{\partial T(x, z)}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(k \frac{\partial T(x, z)}{\partial z} \right) \quad (1)$$

where T is the temperature, ρ and c the lumped density and specific heat for the composite material respectively, k the lumped thermal conductivity in z direction. x and z are respectively the coordinates parallel and perpendicular to the pulling direction (see Figure 2) and U the constant speed along the x -axis at which the composite is pulled. The composite is treated as an infinite slab of finite height W with prescribed temperature at the surfaces, $z = \pm W/2$.

The boundary conditions within the die are presented Figure 2. Lumped properties are calculated with fiber volume fraction evolving from 36% to 55%. The rule of mixture has been used to obtain the homogenized density, and the inverse rule of mixture has been used for the specific heat and the thermal conductivity through the thickness (see [5]).

The numerical solution is obtained with Comsol Multiphysics, a finite element (FE) numerical software. To validate the model, several thermocouples were used to monitor the temperature distribution along the pultrusion line. To do that the thermocouples were attached to the tapes at several positions through the thickness. In this study, the temperature was recorded with profile thickness of 3.2 mm (5 plies) and the thermocouple was inserted between the plies number 2 and 3. Figure 3 shows the comparison between numerical results and thermocouple measurements within the heated die.

Figure 3: Comparison between numerical results and temperature measurements within the heated die

The measurements are consistent with the simulation even if at the heated die entry there is a slight difference (error less than 2%). The reason is that the die wall temperature is assumed uniformly constant whereas in reality the die entry might be cooled by convection. The conclusion is that the heat transfer model is correct within the heated die.

3.2 Coupling with the flow model

The flow model is coupled to the heat transfer model through the viscosity. The polymer viscosity is expressed as a function of the temperature. An exponential model was used:

$$\eta(T) = ae^{-\frac{T}{b}} \quad (2)$$

where η is the polymer viscosity, T the temperature of the fiber/polymer system calculated by the heat transfer model, a and b constant coefficients ($a = 3.106$ Pa.s and $b = 45.45$ K). These coefficients were chosen according to rheologic properties given by Solvay. They lead to a viscosity of 30 Pa.s at 250 °C, 15 Pa.s at 280 °C and 10 Pa.s at 300 °C. The goal is to check the temperature dependent viscosity influence on the impregnation step.

4 MICROGRAPHIC OBSERVATIONS

Several samples were produced with different process parameters combinations. At the end of the pultrusion line after the cooling, samples were cut out from profiles and polished to analyze cross-sections with an optical microscope.

Several micrographs are presented in Figure 4. They were produced at the same pulling speed of 0.7 m/min, with 7 plies of glass fiber tape and with an exit die nominal thickness of 4 mm. But the final thicknesses are different between those three samples. It can be explained by a difference of temperature at the exit of the heated die. Depending on this process parameter, the swelling of the fiber/polymer system at the die exit can differ because of different solidification states. Micrographs in Figure 4 show diverse degrees of saturation. By saturation it is meant impregnation of the fiber bundles. Saturation degrees change between these samples because of the die temperature variations. The saturation is equal to 0 when the bundle is not impregnated (no polymer inside) and equal to 1 when it is fully impregnated. As shown in Figure 5 the inter-tow volumes, which are the channels between the fiber bundles, seem to be completely impregnated by the matrix (matrix appears white on the micrographs). Whereas the intra-tow volumes which are the channels between the fibers within the bundles show different degrees of saturation (porosities appear in black).

Figure 4: Micrographs of pultruded profile sections from left to right from the less saturated to the most saturated (profiles produced with 7 plies, $U = 0,7$ m/min, $W = 4$ mm but with different die exit temperatures)

Figure 5: Enlargements of the pultruded profile sections shown in figure 4

The main observation is that during the impregnation of the woven fiber reinforcement, a dual-scale flow takes place. The polymer seems to have no difficulty to flow within the inter-tow volumes whereas it takes more time to impregnate the intra-tow volumes. As it will be seen in the next section, it can be assumed that at the heated die entry the composite is already macroscopically impregnated but bundles are unsaturated. This assumption means that the matrix fills the inter-tow volumes as soon as the tapes enter the die, whereas it takes some time to fill the bundles and depending on the process parameters it might be impossible to get a complete impregnation of the bundles.

These micrographs give process modeling indications of the occurring phenomena. The flow modeling approach might not be to determine a flow front location as the profile faces a rapid macroflow followed by a slower unsaturated microflow. Since the stack of fabrics is pulled and travels through the melt polymer, the notion of flow front is replaced by the notion of saturation. Therefore, the material (reinforcement and polymer) can be considered as an unsaturated porous medium that is consolidating along the die. Then the principal modeling aim is the prediction of the degree of saturation evolution along the die.

5 UNSATURATED FLOW MODELING ADAPTED TO PULTRUSION PROCESS

During pultrusion with direct thermoplastic injection within the die, the polymer movement will be modeled as a flow within dual-scale porous media. As shown above, within the heated die, the fiber bundles can be considered completely surrounded by the liquid polymer and unsaturated. Then as the fiber bundles go through the tapered portion, the cross-sectional area becomes smaller, the bundles begin to saturate and the excess polymer starts to flow backward.

5.1 Dual scale flow model

In this study a double scale porosity model is used. A sink term is added to the mass conservation equation:

$$\nabla \cdot u = -q(P, S) \quad (3)$$

where q is the sink term which represents the absorption of the polymer by the bundles, P the macroscopic pressure and S the bundles saturation (equals to 0 if not saturated, 1 if fully saturated). This approach was used by several authors such as Parnas and Phelan [6], Chan and Morgan [7], Pillai and Advani [8], Bréard et al. [9] or Gourichon et al. [3]. Park and Lee [10] also mentioned this approach in the review of the unsaturated flow in liquid composites.

At the macroscale, Darcy's law is applied to model the flow between the bundles. The macroscopic permeability is chosen considering the bundles as impermeable. The flow at the microscale is modeled within the sink term q . The sink term which represents the rate of the polymer volumetric ratio which flows from inter-tow volumes into intra-tow volumes can be expressed as a function of the saturation kinetics:

$$q(P, S) = \epsilon_{micro}(1 - \epsilon_{macro}) \frac{dS}{dt} \quad (4)$$

where ϵ_{micro} and ϵ_{macro} are respectively the porosity within fiber bundles and within the macroscopic gap. A microscopic flow model will be described in section 6.

5.2 Governing equations

Thanks to the volume averaging method by [11] and [12] and the change of variables between time t and x -coordinate ($x = Ut$), the flow model equations can be derived as follow. The mass conservation in equation (3) becomes:

$$\nabla \cdot \langle u \rangle = -q \quad (5)$$

where $\langle u \rangle$ is the volume averaged polymer velocity in the inter-tow volumes. The sink term expression in equation (4) becomes:

$$q = \epsilon_{micro}(1 - \epsilon_{macro})U \frac{dS}{dx} \quad (6)$$

The polymer flow at the macroscopic scale during pultrusion can be modeled as Darcy's law in a moving frame with a constant speed. The equation was derived by [11]:

$$\langle u \rangle - \epsilon_{macro}U = -\frac{K}{\eta} \nabla P \quad (7)$$

where K is the macroscopic permeability tensor considering bundles as impermeable. In this study an isotropic permeability K was used. Because of the tapered region in the die, the permeability is x -coordinate dependent, since the fiber volume fraction increases along the die. Results obtained by Comas-Cardona et al. [13] with glass fiber plain weave were used. An extrapolation was made to obtain permeability values for low fiber volume fractions (under 45%). The permeability values used in this study had been: 10^{-7} m^2 at the die entry (fiber volume fraction of 36 %) and 10^{-10} m^2 at the exit (fiber volume fraction of 55 %). And the logarithm of the permeability is changing linearly from -7 to -10 in between.

The boundary conditions applied to the domain are represented in Figure 6. As already explained, the tows saturation is supposed equal to zero at the die entry. Then the pressure is supposed to be null at the entry and the exit, and polymer velocity normal to the die walls is equal to zero (no in or out flux through the die walls).

Figure 6: Boundary conditions applied to the heated die domain for the flow model

Equations (2 and 5 - 7) are coupled and solved with Comsol Multiphysics software through finite element method. But an expression for the saturation kinetics is still necessary. A saturation model is presented in the next section.

6 SINK TERM MODELING

The sink term, added to the continuity equation, represents the absorption rate of polymer by the tows. First an analytic approach described by Parnas and Phelan [6] is adapted to model the tows impregnation. Then a new approach for the sink term is proposed taking into account the surface exchange evolution between the tows and inter-tow volumes in the tapered die.

To solve equations (5 - 7), an expression for the saturation kinetics is necessary. Parnas and Phelan [6] suggested considering the tows as cylinders. They derived an expression for the penetrating flow of resin into the fiber tow depicted in Figure 7. At the boundary of the tow the macroscopic pressure P_0 in the inter-tow volumes is applied. r_0 is the equivalent cylinder tow radius and r_f is the local flow front location in the cylinder. The dashed line represents the local flow front. The pressure at the tow center P_∞ , ahead of the flow front, can be assumed null (or equal to the atmospheric pressure) within the pultrusion die because the air can escape from the die entry (intra-tow volumes are assumed as continuous channels along the die).

Darcy's law for radial flow and derived with the volume averaging method by Tucker and Dessenberger [11] and Pillai [12], relates the radial fluid velocity to the pressure gradient:

$$\langle v_r \rangle = -\frac{K}{\eta} \nabla P \quad (8)$$

where $\langle v_r \rangle$ is the radial fluid velocity flowing within the fibers, K the transverse tow permeability, η the fluid viscosity and P the fluid pressure.

Figure 7: Radial flow into a cylinder fiber tow
(P_0 pressure outside the tows, r_0 tow radius and r_f local flow front location)

After appropriate integration the following expression is obtained:

$$\frac{dS}{dt} = -\frac{4K}{(1 - V_{f0})r_0^2} \frac{P_0}{\eta} \frac{1}{\ln(1 - S)} \quad (9)$$

This expression gives the saturation kinetics within the tows. It depends on K the tow permeability, V_{f0} the fiber volume fraction within the tow, r_0 the tow radius, P_0 the macroscopic pressure given by equations (5) and (7) and η the polymer viscosity. A change of variable is necessary to substitute the expression into equation (6):

$$\frac{dS}{dx} = -\frac{4K}{U(1 - V_{f0})r_0^2} \frac{P_0}{\eta} \frac{1}{\ln(1 - S)} \quad (10)$$

where U is the pulling speed which is constant.

In the previous approach the tows are considered constantly surrounded by the polymer which fills the inter-tow volumes. But as the tows moves in the die, the fiber/resin system is compressed in the tapered section and the tows are compacted to each other. So the exchange surfaces between the tows and the inter-tow volumes change along the die. As soon as a tow is in contact with another tow, the surface exchange decreases [3]. This phenomenon is not taken into account in the previous model.

7 RESULTS AND VALIDATION

The aim is to predict the saturation level (residual porosity level) of the fiber tows at the exit of the heated die. The influences of processing parameters are analyzed. Here results are shown in Figure 8 for sensitivity of die geometry. More results are given in Babeau et al. [14], such as for the sensitivity of pulling speed, polymer viscosity and temperature distribution.

Two die geometry parameters were studied: the taper angle and the taper length. These results were obtained with a pulling speed of 0.5 m/min and a polymer viscosity of 15 Pa.s.

The Figure 8 shows that a taper angle increase induces a pressure and a saturation increase. So the taper angle is a critical process parameter. However it is important to remind that a too high pressure in the die might damage the tapes. So compromise has to be found for the taper angle to get a good saturation without too much pressure.

Figure 8: Pressure and saturation results at the profile center for several heated die exit temperatures

A similar result is shown in Figure 9 for the taper length. The vertical lines in the Figure 9 represent the end of the taper length for each value. As expected, the longer the taper, the higher the polymer pressure. And it has a direct influence on the saturation. Moreover the time of residency increases also when the taper is longer, so the polymer has more time to flow within the tows.

Figure 9: Pressure and saturation results at the profile center for several heated die length

The conclusion of these results is that the die geometry is a critical process parameter. Depending on the targeted pulling speed and the polymer viscosity, the right combination of taper angle and length has to be chosen to get a pultruded profile with limited porosity.

8 CONCLUSION

Such models help to better understand the thermoplastic pultrusion process, to optimize the process parameters. The final goal is to manufacture pultruded profiles with the lowest residual porosity with pulling speeds compatible with an industrial process (speeds > 1 m/min).

Knowing that the temperature might be an important parameter to get a good saturation in pultruded profile, the first step of the study was the heat transfer modeling. A model was implemented and validated through temperature measures along the processing pultrusion line.

Then micrographs of pultruded profiles were observed, and it has been noticed that the polymer impregnated easily the macroscopic channels. So the main hypothesis for the flow model was to assume that the inter-tow volumes are impregnated as soon as the fiber reinforcements enter the die. The goal of the flow model was to capture the saturation of the fiber tows along the die. An unsaturated flow approach with a sink term was implemented as well as a coupling with the heat transfer with a temperature dependent viscosity. The originality of this work also stands into the changes of variables to simulate the steady state of the continuous process which exhibits consolidation of an unsaturated double scale medium. The simulation results show that the process parameter that has the main influence on the profile degree of saturation is the die geometry, such as the taper angle and the taper length. The temperature of the die exit has only a limited influence and the pulling speed or the polymer viscosity does not change the final degree of saturation in the implemented model. To valid these models, an image analysis was conducted to measure accurately final saturation degrees in the profile.

Using the work by [3], a new approach for the sink term in the mass balance was proposed. It takes into account the actual surface exchange between two porous media and the potential exchanges between them. Thus the model shows the influence of the tows compaction along the die on the final saturation. To quantify this evolution along the die, micrographs were done and through image analysis, it was possible to capture the compaction of the tows along the tapered die (

Figure 10).

Figure 10: Image analysis done on micrographs along the consolidated tapered profile showing the compaction evolution (from left to right: $V_f = 40\%$, 44% , 57%)

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REFERENCES

- [1] A.L. Jeswani and J.A. Roux, Impact of Fiber Volume Fraction and Resin Viscosity With Die-Detached Tapered Chamber in Resin Injection Pultrusion, *Journal of Manufacturing Science and Engineering*, **132**, 2010, pp. 021007.
- [2] K.M. Pillai, Governing equations for unsaturated flow through woven fiber mats. Part 1. Isothermal flows, *Composites Part A*, **33**, 2002, pp. 1007-1019.
- [3] B. Gourichon, C. Binetruy and P. Krawczak, A new numerical procedure to predict dynamic void content in liquid composite molding, *Composites Part A*, **37**, 2006, pp. 1961-1969.
- [4] B.T. Aström and R.B. Pipes, A modeling approach to thermoplastic pultrusion. I: Formulation of models, *Polymer Composites*, **14**, 1993, pp. 173-183.
- [5] M. Thomas, Propriétés thermiques de matériaux composites : caractérisation expérimentale et approche microstructurale, *PhD Thesis*, Université de Nantes, 2008.
- [6] R.S. Parnas and F.R. Phelan, The effect of heterogeneous porous media on mold filling in resin transfer molding, *SAMPE quarterly*, January 1991, pp. 53-60.
- [7] A.W. Chan and R.J. Morgan, Tow impregnation during resin transfer molding of bi-directional nonwoven fabrics, *Polymer Composites*, **14**, 1993, pp. 335-340.
- [8] K.M. Pillai and S.G. Advani, A model for unsaturated flow in woven fiber preforms during mold filling in resin transfer molding, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **32**, 1998, pp. 1753-1783.
- [9] J. Bréard, Y. Henzel, F. Trochu and R. Gauvin, Analysis of dynamic flows through porous media. Part I: Comparison between saturated and unsaturated flows in fibrous reinforcements, *Polymer Composites*, **24**, 2003, pp. 391-408.
- [10] C.H. Park and W.I. Lee, Modeling void formation and unsaturated flow in liquid composite molding processes: a survey and review, *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, **30**, 2011, pp. 957-977.
- [11] C.L. Tucker III and R.B. Dessenberger, Governing equations for flow and heat transfer in stationary fiber beds, in: S.G. Advani (Ed.), *Flow and Rheology in Polymer Composites Manufacturing*, Elsevier Science Publishers, 1994, pp. 257-323.
- [12] K.M. Pillai, Governing equations for unsaturated flow through woven fiber mats. Part 1. Isothermal flows, *Composites Part A*, **33**, 2002, pp. 1007-1019.
- [13] S. Comas-Cardona, C. Binetruy and P. Krawczak, Unidirectional compression of fibre reinforcements. Part 2: A continuous permeability tensor measurement, *Composites Science and Technology*, **67**, 2007, pp. 638-645.
- [14] A. Babeau, S. Comas-Cardona, C. Binetruy and G. Orange, Modeling of heat transfer and unsaturated flow in woven fiber reinforcements during direct injection-pultrusion process of thermoplastic composites, *Composites Part A*, in press.